

Workshop 3

AGU Ethics in AI/ML

February 13, 2023

Virtual: 10:00 to 16:00 ET

<https://agu.zoom.us/j/98071558134?pwd=WGhZU0V4Wm1tTUxOOHhENCtQYXAxdz09>

Our Funder: NASA (80NSSC22K0734)

<https://data.agu.org/ethics-ai-ml/>

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Meeting Code of Conduct

Expected behavior

1. Treat everyone with respect.
2. Use good practices for intercultural collaborations.
3. Be mindful of your surroundings and of your fellow participants.
4. Provide your true professional identity and affiliation.
5. Respect copying and use of presented materials and ideas as indicated by [AGU's Guidelines on Photography and Social Media](#), including knowing when you may need to obtain permission regarding copying materials.
6. Respect the rules and policies of AGU's meeting space, hotels, online platform, or any other related venue.
7. Be Accountable: When we as organizers or participants fail to meet these guidelines, work together to identify problems and adjust policy and practice together.

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Meeting Agenda

Time (EST)	Agenda Item
10:00am	Welcome & Project Recap
10:15am 75 min	Discuss Feedback and Assign Action Items Joel Cutcher-Gershenfeld
11:30am 60 min	Lunch Break
12:30pm 90 min	Working Groups <ul style="list-style-type: none">Review & address feedback on assigned modules/principles & responsibilities
2:00pm 15 min	Break
2:15pm 75 min	Group Discussion
3:30pm 30 min	Closing & Next Steps <ul style="list-style-type: none">Timeline to finalize document; plan for use and tracking impact
4:00pm	Adjourn

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Project Recap

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The Team

Steering Committee

Ayris A Narock (NASA / ADNET SYSTEMS INC), Micaela Parker (Academic Data Science Alliance), Yuhan Douglas Rao (North Carolina Institute for Climate Studies), Thomas Donaldson (The Wharton School, Legal Studies & Business Ethics Department), Guido Cervone (Penn State, Department of Geography), Lance A. Waller (Emory University)

Editorial Team

Guido Cervone (Penn State, Department of Geography), Yuhan Douglas Rao (North Carolina Institute for Climate Studies), Micaela Parker (Academic Data Science Alliance), Joel Cutcher-Gershenfeld (Brandeis University), Caroline Coward (JPL Library), Jeanne Holm (City of Los Angeles), Ryan McGranaghan (Atmospheric and Space Technology Research Associates, LLC), Delia Pembrey (Technology and Digital Programmes Services Australia), Ge Peng (NASA MSFC IMPACT University of Alabama, Huntsville), Shashi Shekhar (University of Minnesota), Christopher Wirz (UCAR)

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AI/ML Ethics

NASA-funded grant to:

Engage a multi-disciple group of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) stakeholders and others to **develop a set of principles and responsibilities for using artificial intelligence and machine learning in Earth, space, and environmental science-focused research.**

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Work So Far:

- Funded by NASA SMD (80NSSC22K0734)
- Steering Committee
- Survey / Analysis
- Two Workshops
 - Diverse Participation (Geography, Gender, Career Stage, Race/Ethnicity, Scientific Discipline)
- Editorial Team Meetings / Draft Document
- AGU Town Hall
- Invite Community Feedback
- **Workshop 3 - Finalize** ← **Now!!**
- Promote & Publish

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AGU Next Steps:

- Determine best approach on how to include principles and responsibilities in our “AGU Scientific Integrity and Professional Ethics” guidance
- Determine best approach for further developing and offering the educational modules
- Promote to our Members

Seven Modules:

- *Module 1:* Transparency, Documentating, and Reporting
- *Module 2:* Intentionality, Interpretability, Explainability, Reproducibility, and Replicability
- *Module 3:* Risk, Bias, and Impacts
- *Module 4:* Trust and AI/ML
- *Module 5:* Participatory Methods and Domain Expertise
- *Module 6:* Outreach, Training, and Leading Practices
- *Module 7:* Organization and Institution; Society and Funder Guidance

Common Format

- Module Focus
- Module Key Points
- Module Learning Objectives
- Module Vision
- Module Definitions
- Module Principles
- Module Responsibilities and Leading Practices
- Module Use Cases and Illustrative Examples
- Module FAQs

Feedback on AI/ML Modules

See Workshop 3 Folder: Feedback to Address

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/19hTVhuWT5VLTX-VjrdDPtA0PZLnNkcKf2PUc4s0SDK4/edit#heading=h.deopmwv6axbd>

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Feedback - to address (slide 1)

- How does this document specifically apply to ESS?
- Relating to how to apply AI in the practice of science - How to embrace new technologies while still maintaining transparency/trust? Hard to evaluate what is 'real' and what is 'hype' in AI/ML.
- 'Explainable' AI/XAI - what are our recommendations on using this?
- How can we make these ethical principles accessible and intelligible to researchers who may be using the outcome of AI/ML work without being conversant with the tool (and its limitations/technicalities/ethical quandaries)?
- Can we identify some exemplars in research to help researchers understand how ethics in AI/ML differs from ethics in 'regular' science?
- What is the researcher responsibility for ethics?
- *For future directions:* Is there a checklist for the researcher to use?

Instructions for Breakout Groups

- Please join a Breakout Group that corresponds to the module you'd like to work on.
Working Groups:
Breakout Group 1 - Transparency, Documenting, and Reporting
Breakout Group 2 - Intentionality, Interpretability, Explainability, Reproducibility, and Replicability
Breakout Group 3 - Risk, Bias, Impacts
Breakout Group 4 - Trust in AI/ML
Breakout Group 5 - Outreach, Training, and Leading Practices
Breakout Group 6 - Participatory Methods and Domain Expertise
Breakout Group 7 - Considerations for Organizations, Institutions, Publishers, Societies, and Funders
- During the working group breakout session, review your module and incorporate any assigned feedback. If anything needs more discussion, leave a comment noting that.
- Be prepared to discuss your changes and the status of the module when we return from the breakout sessions at 2:15 PM ET.
- Document to edit in Google Drive: [AI-ML Ethics Modules for ESES - Workshop 3 - Feb 2023](#)

Breakout Groups

Working Groups:

Breakout Group 1 - Transparency, Documenting, and Reporting

Breakout Group 2 - Intentionality, Interpretability, Explainability, Reproducibility, and Replicability

Breakout Group 3 - Risk, Bias, Impacts

Breakout Group 4 - Trust in AI/ML

Breakout Group 5 - Outreach, Training, and Leading Practices

Breakout Group 6 - Participatory Methods and Domain Expertise

Breakout Group 7 - Considerations for Organizations, Institutions, Publishers, Societies, and Funders

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1 Hour Lunch Break

Please return at 12:30 PM ET and enter your
Breakout Group:

Breakout Group 1 - Transparency, Documenting, and Reporting

Breakout Group 2 - Intentionality, Interpretability, Explainability, Reproducibility, and Replicability

Breakout Group 3 - Risk, Bias, Impacts

Breakout Group 4 - Trust in AI/ML

Breakout Group 5 - Outreach, Training, and Leading Practices

Breakout Group 6 - Participatory Methods and Domain Expertise

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15 minute break

Please return at 2:15 PM ET for Group Discussion.

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Group Discussion

- Breakout Groups Report: (10 min each)
 - Breakout Group 1 - Transparency, Documenting, and Reporting**
 - Breakout Group 2 - Intentionality, Interpretability, Explainability, Reproducibility, and Replicability**
 - Breakout Group 3 - Risk, Bias, Impacts
 - Breakout Group 4 - Trust in AI/ML
 - Breakout Group 5 - Outreach, Training, and Leading Practices**
 - Breakout Group 6 - Participatory Methods and Domain Expertise**
 - Breakout Group 7 - Considerations for Organizations, Institutions, Publishers, Societies, and Funders**

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Closing & Next Steps

- Discuss next steps and timeline to finalize document
- Discuss plan for use and tracking impact
- Schedule any future work needed

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Thank you

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